

9,10-[1,4-Dihydrosubstituted-naphthalene-2-oxo-*endo/exo*-1,4-diyl]-*N*-arylsuccinimide : Configurational Assignment by Pmr Spectroscopy

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Diels-Alder adducts of maleic anhydride with 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene, 2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene and 6-bromo-2-naphthol have been converted into their *o*-tolylimide and 1-naphthylimide derivatives. Restricted rotation and non-planar conformations about the aryl C-N bond in *ortho*-substituted arylimides have been employed in solving structural problem by pmr spectroscopy.

DIELS-Alder adducts from polynuclear dienes with appropriate dienophiles have been studied with particular reference to the spatial alignment of the dienophile moiety giving rise to either *endo* or *exo* configuration^{1,2}. Assignment of configurations of dihydroxynaphthalene have been mostly carried out with the help of uv absorption and CD spectra and also by chemical methods². The methods used so far are rather indirect. The assignment of *endo* and *exo* configuration of some Diels-Alder adducts obtained from dihydroxynaphthalene with maleic anhydride was based on lactone formation resulting from NaBH₄ reduction of the *exo* isomer containing a reducible group. We feel that a direct method for structural assignment would be more useful.

In this communication the applicability of the N-C bond conformations of the derived aryl imides in the structural assignment of these compounds and hence of the Diels-Alder adducts (2a-c and 3a, b) is discussed. It is evident that this system enables the assignment of correct configuration to either *endo* or *exo* adduct without a comparison with the pattern of the corresponding isomer, and therefore this method offers a distinct advantage over the earlier methods especially when one of the isomers is not formed. Restricted rotation and non-planar conformations about the N-N bond³ and the aryl C-N⁴ bond have been used for configurational assignments of Diels-Alder adducts. *ortho*-Substituted-phenylimide (4) is quite diagnostic and effective in the structural elucidation which can easily be obtained from Diels-Alder adducts in one step under ordinary experimental conditions. *ortho*-Substituted-anilides of 2,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-maleic anhydride (5a, b and 6a, b), 2,6-dihydroxynaphthalene-maleic anhydride (7a, b and 8a, b) and 6-bromo-2-naphthol-maleic anhydride (9a, b) have been prepared and their pmr spectral data (Table 1) are discussed in the light of their configurational assignment.

Results and Discussion

The spectrum of the *o*-toluidide derivative (5a) showed two singlets for the *o*-tolylmethyl protons at δ 1.03 and 2.01. In the other derivative (6a), the *o*-tolylmethyl protons also appeared as two singlets at δ 2.08 and 2.10 along with other normal proton resonances. These spectral multiplicities are due to the hindered rotation about aryl C-N bond and the existence of the two atropisomers (10) and (11) is indicated. On the basis of shielding effect on the *syn*-*o*-tolyl protons by the cage-moiety (11), a reasonable assignment of the configuration of the adduct is possible. A high degree of shielding on the *o*-methyl protons ($\Delta\nu=76$ Hz, the difference in chemical shift between two singlet δ 1.03 and 2.01 of *o*-methyl protons) by the cage benzo-ring suggests the *endo*-configuration for 5a, while a low degree of shielding on the *o*-methyl protons ($\Delta\nu=18$ Hz, the difference in chemical shift between two singlet δ 2.08 and 2.10 of *o*-methyl protons) suggests the *exo*-configuration for 6a. The *endo*-configuration for 5a is further demonstrated by the observation of a multiplet at δ 5.53 (0.58H) which could arise from the shielding of the *ortho*-hydrogen of the *N*-phenyl by the cage benzo-ring in the atropisomer 10.

The spectra of 1-naphthylimide derivatives of the isomeric adducts (*endo/exo*) are diagnostic in the configurational assignment of the adducts as the 2,3-benzo group of the 1-naphthylimide strongly influences the resonances of the cage protons providing fruitful results.

The pmr spectrum of 5b showed a multiplet at δ 2.10-3.02 for the methylene protons (C-3) and a multiplet at δ 5.38 (0.68H) for the *ortho* proton of the naphthylimide, while that of the isomeric adduct 6b showed a broad multiplet at δ 1.56-3.06 for the said methylene protons. As upfield chemical shift for C-3 protons in 6b is caused by the shielding of

TABLE I—PMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	X (CH ₃ or benzo)	o-H of the N-aryl	1,4,9,10-H	3-CH ₂	5-8 and N-phenyl (<i>m</i> and <i>p</i>)	R
5a	189-90	1.03, 2.01 (3H, 2×s)	5.53, 6.75-7.45 (1H, 2×m)	3.52-4.12 (4H, m)	2.07-2.91 (2H, m)	6.75-7.45 (6H, m)	8.18 (1H, s)
5b	183-84	7.21-7.58 (4H, m)	5.38, 7.21-7.58 (1H, 2×m)	3.51-4.20 (4H, m)	2.10-3.02 (2H, m)	7.21-7.58 (5H, m)	8.20 (1H, s)
6a	203-05	2.08, 2.10 (3H, 2×s)	6.74-7.52 (1H, m)	3.48-4.23 (4H, m)	2.08-2.78 (2H, m)	6.74-7.52 (6H, m)	8.33 (1H, s)
6b	209-11	6.82-7.63 (4H, m)	6.82-7.60 (1H, m)	3.50-4.40 (4H, m)	1.56-3.06 (2H, m)	6.82-7.63 (5H, m)	8.35 (1H, s)
7a	196-97	1.04-2.02 (3H, 2×s)	5.53, 7.02-7.86 (1H, 2×m)	3.52-4.45 (4H, m)	2.10-2.95 (2H, m)	7.02-7.86 (6H, m)	8.33 (1H, s)
7b	214-15	6.63-7.52 (4H, m)	5.45, 6.63-7.52 (1H, 2×m)	3.54-4.46 (4H, m)	2.07-3.01 (2H, m)	6.63-7.52 (5H, m)	8.36 (1H, s)
8a	205-06	2.08, 2.10 (3H, 2×s)	7.10-7.85 (1H, m)	3.54-4.50 (4H, m)	2.02-2.85 (2H, m)	7.10-7.85 (6H, m)	8.32 (1H, s)
8b	200-01	6.95-7.84 (4H, m)	6.95-7.84 (1H, m)	3.52-4.48 (4H, m)	1.55-3.03 (2H, m)	6.95-7.84 (5H, m)	8.33 (1H, s)
9a	210-11	1.09, 2.04 (3H, 2×s)	5.55, 6.71-7.82 (1H, 2×m)	3.38-4.33 (4H, m)	2.16-2.91 (2H, m)	6.71-7.82 (6H, m)	—
9b	203-04	6.85, 7.88 (4H, m)	5.46, 6.85-7.88 (1H, 2×m)	3.42-4.38 (4H, m)	2.10-3.01 (2H, m)	6.85-7.88 (5H, m)	—

*All compounds showed satisfactory C and H analyses.

one of the methylene protons by the 2,3-benzo group and the adduct could be assigned as *exo*, while a downfield chemical shift for the C-3 protons coupled with an upfield chemical shift of the *ortho* naphthyl proton in **5b** suggests the *endo* configuration. The pmr spectra of *o*-toluidine derivatives (**7a** and **8a**) exhibited similar pattern. These isomeric compounds showed two singlets for *o*-tolylmethyl protons with an internal chemical shift of 76 and 18 Hz respectively along with other proton resonances. These observations suggest the shielding of the *o*-methyl protons ($\Delta\nu=76$ Hz) by the cage benzo ring, thus suggesting the *endo* configuration for **7a**, hence for **2b** as well. The isomeric derivative **8a**, hence the parent adduct **3b**, is assigned the *exo* configuration.

The pmr spectra of **7b** and **8b** exhibited features similar to those of **5b** and **6b**. An upfield chemical shift for the C-3 methylene protons suggests the *exo* configuration for **8b**, while a downfield shift for C-3 methylene protons and shielding of the *ortho*-naphthyl proton by benzo-ring indicate the *endo* configuration for **7b**.

The pmr spectrum of the *o*-toluidine derivative (**9a**) showed two singlets for the *o*-tolylmethyl protons at δ 1.09 and 2.04, a multiplet of 0.55H intensity at δ 5.55 and 6.45H intensity at δ 6.71-7.82 for aromatic protons along with other proton resonances. On the basis of the shielding of *o*-methyl protons ($\Delta\nu=85$ Hz) by cage benzo-ring, the *endo* configuration of **9a**, hence of the adduct **2c** has been suggested. The possibility of formation of the *exo*-adduct is eliminated, since for such a product one would expect low degree of shielding of the *o*-methyl protons by the cage moiety.

The pmr spectrum of **9b** further suggests the formation of *endo*-adduct only. The spectrum showed the normal proton resonances along with a multiplet for C-3 methylene protons at δ 2.10-3.01

and a shielded *ortho*-naphthyl proton at δ 5.46 (0.68H).

Experimental

Pmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Zeol FX-90 MHz spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as

internal standard and ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer.

The known maleic anhydride adducts **2a-c**, **3a** and **3b** were prepared as per literature² and the structures were confirmed by comparing the m.p., ir and elemental (C, H) analysis data with those reported in the literature²: **2a** δ 2.02–2.95 (2H, m, C-3), 3.58–3.90 (4H, m, C-1, C-4, C-9 and C-10), 6.75–7.32 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.15 (1H, s, OH); **2b** δ 1.95–2.95 (3H, m, C-3), 3.55–4.50 (4H, m, C-1, C-4, C-9 and C-10), 7.10–7.85 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.30 (1H, s, OH); **2c** δ 2.07–3.10 (2H, m, C-3), 3.64–4.58 (4H, m, C-1, C-4, C-9 and C-10) and 7.09–7.92 (3H, m, ArH); **3a** δ 2.05–3.90 (6H, m, C-1, C-3, C-4, C-9 and C-10), 6.70–7.32 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.33 (1H, s, OH); **3b** δ 2.05–3.05 (2H, m, C-3), 3.60–4.53 (4H, m, C-1, C-4, C-9 and C-10), 7.06–7.90 (3H, m, ArH) and 8.32 (1H, s, OH).

Arylimide derivatives (5a–9a and 5b–9b): The toluidides (**5a–9a**) and naphthylimides (**5b–9b**)

derivatives were obtained by heating the isomeric adducts with equimolar amounts of *o*-toluidine and 1-naphthylamine respectively, at 120–30° for 3 h and the resulting solids were recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

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